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METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RETAIL MARKETING AND TRADING SYSTEM.

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Abstract: This article analyzes the methodological foundations for developing marketing activities in the retail industry in the current context. The study examines the formation of marketing strategies based on an in-depth study of the domestic market, consumer behavior, market segmentation, and the competitive environment.

Key words: retail, sales process, advertising, sales efficiency, e-commerce, sales market development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy sharoitda chakana savdo tizimida marketing faoliyatini rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslarini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda ichki bozor, iste'molchi xulq-atvori, bozor segmentatsiyasi va raqobat muhitini chuqur o'rganish asosida marketing strategiyalarini shakllantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: chakana savdo, sotish jarayoni, reklama, savdo samaradorligi, elektron tijorat, savdo bozorini rivojlantirish.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются методологические основы развития маркетинговой деятельности в розничной торговле в современных условиях. В исследовании рассматриваются вопросы формирования маркетинговых стратегий на основе углубленного изучения внутреннего рынка, поведения потребителей, сегментации рынка и конкурентной среды.

Ключевые слова: розничная торговля, процесс продаж, реклама, эффективность продаж, электронная коммерция, развитие рынка сбыта.

INTRODUCTION

In modern global economic relations, retail trade is an important part of the national economy, playing a decisive role in meeting the daily needs of the population, developing entrepreneurship and strengthening market infrastructure. In particular, improving the retail system through effective marketing mechanisms allows for increased competitiveness, in-depth study of consumer needs and adaptation of trade enterprises to market processes.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev is constantly setting priority areas for the development of the sector. Decree UP No. 5564 of October 30, 2018 "On measures to further liberalize trade and develop competition in commodity markets" is one of the important documents aimed at expanding market mechanisms in the trade sector, simplifying regulations for entrepreneurs, and creating a competitive environment. This decree serves to increase the efficiency of the domestic market by ensuring that trade entities operate in conditions of free competition.[1]

Also, the recent Presidential Decree No. UP 67 dated April 18, 2025 "On measures to stimulate trade and industrial policy, increase production and exports" has encouraged reforms such as simplifying the procedure for internal trade and modernizing the process of registering product certificates. These documents will serve to organize the marketing and business processes of retail entities in a more favorable environment.[2]

Other documents adopted by the President on market liberalization and improvement of the competitive environment, including the decisions currently being taken on the path to WTO membership, are aimed at adapting the national trade system to global standards and developing it through effective marketing strategies.

Therefore, the development of a methodology for the development of retail marketing is inextricably linked to national government policies, and this topic requires comprehensive research.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Sinyayeva I.M. paid special attention to the issues of market research, supply and demand analysis, market segmentation, and working with target consumers in retail and wholesale trade. The role of sales assortment formation, pricing policy, sales channel management, and sales promotion mechanisms in marketing is also revealed.[3]

Zavyalov P. S. The book emphasizes the role of consumer behavior in retail and wholesale trade, the selection of sales channels, and incentive measures aimed at increasing sales. The manual is an important methodological resource for a systematic understanding of sales processes and their optimization from a marketing point of view.[4]

Grigoryan Ye. S. systematically covers the theoretical foundations of marketing communications and their practical application in sales activities. In addition, he analyzes the interrelationships of advertising, sales promotion, public relations, personal selling, and digital communications.[5]

Kadyrov A. Q. Justifies the role and importance of domestic trade in the national economy, paying special attention to the issues of improving trade infrastructure, developing a competitive environment, and ensuring the effective functioning of market mechanisms. The work scientifically covers the economic mechanisms of retail trade, including price formation, supply and demand balance, quality of trade services, and methods of supporting trade entities.[6]

Rakhimov Sh. K., studying the dependence of the trade services market on internal and external factors, pays special attention to the issues of improving service quality, satisfying consumer needs and ensuring competitiveness. The work presents methodological recommendations for optimizing the marketing tools, assortment of services, pricing policy and service process of retail trade services.[7]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used the following scientific methods to systematically analyze retail marketing development processes and develop effective methodological approaches:

1. Analytical method - the current state of the domestic market, the retail system and consumer behavior were analyzed, sales indicators and the results of marketing decisions were evaluated.

2. Comparative analysis - domestic and foreign retail marketing experiences were compared, which served to identify effective strategies.

3. Empirical research - questionnaires, interviews and the practical activities of retail enterprises were studied, and the impact of marketing instruments was determined.

This methodology serves to strengthen the theoretical foundations of retail marketing development, develop practical recommendations and increase the competitiveness of the retail system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the current stage of trade development, as a result of the widespread and effective use of marketing solutions, high growth rates of retail trade volumes are being formed. The rapid development of the trade sector and the steady increase in real incomes of the population make the domestic consumer market one of the most promising and attractive in the world. Trade acts as a leading branch of marketing in the economy. It is retail that maximally orients local producers to take into account the requirements of society.

Retailers are mobile, low-cost, and have great flexibility to adapt to market changes.

Retail is a system of retailing (retail trade is a small business associated with the sale of goods in quantities for personal and family use). Retail is based on the theory of personal choice, based on the principle of consumer preference. Therefore, retail is a social expression of the quality of life of society. Retail is an exchange of goods aimed at satisfying people's needs through the free sale of goods and services that are valuable to the buyer. (Table 1). [3]

Retail trade classification signs

№	Classification symbol	Characteristic features
1	Concentration and location	Individual store placement Grouping of retail outlets (network sales)
2	Type of assortment being sold	Specialized Universal Mix

3	<p>Sales services form:</p> <p>a) a) methods of selling goods</p> <p>b) additional services</p>	<p>a) individual service (over the counter)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - self-service - open display - sale of goods by samples or catalogs - sale of goods on a pre-order basis - direct sales by telephone, Internet <p>b) consultations; sample display</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tailoring of sewing products to customer sizes - cutting and packaging of food products according to customer orders - festive packaging, order delivery - flexible forms of payment for purchases (credit, discount cards) - quality, return, repair and service guarantee
4	Types of retail establishments	Tonnar, pavilion, gastronomer, department store, universam, Bentham, trading house, shopping center, discounter, super- and hypermarkets, boutiques
5	Retail price level	<p>low („second hand“; discount)</p> <p>high (prices in boutiques, super- and hypermarkets, shopping centers, department stores, company stores)</p>

Retail trade is understood as an activity related to the sale of goods for subsequent personal, family, household or other similar purposes. The classification features of retail trade include: concentration and location; type of assortment sold, forms of trade services, types of enterprises, retail price level

The effectiveness of sales activities is directly dependent on the constantly changing consumer mood and new ways of doing business. Retail trade has various business forms aimed at satisfying the end consumer through marketing activities through the distribution channel, such as organizing goods and services to the final consumer along a multi-stage distribution chain. The distribution chain itself consists of a number of links connecting raw material producers, wholesalers and transport companies with the retailer and the final consumer.

Retail business combines the interests of the seller in making a profit and the needs of the buyer in obtaining high-quality goods and services, and identifying and satisfying customer demand is the main task of marketing.

At each stage of creating a sales process, marketing solves certain business management tasks, which allows you to increase profits and actively respond to market trends.

The scheme of the organizational stages of marketing in the retail system is shown in Figure 1.[4]

Figure 1 - Organization of marketing activities in retail

In addition to taking into account other and internal factors, it is important to determine the location of the point of sale, taking into account the preferences of potential consumers and the possibility of opening a retail store. The second stage involves the development, systematic and adaptive use of marketing research tools. The organization of the sales process is accompanied by the formation of a product policy. At the same time, it is necessary to analyze the attractiveness of the assortment in terms of the level of demand, the ability to manage consumers and the profitability of sales.

The third stage of marketing implementation in retail is the assessment of the effectiveness of financial and economic indicators, including: revenue, total costs, turnover, profit and profitability of sales operations. At this stage, it is very important to ensure a unified sales system based on automated accounting and control of accounting and cash transactions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It was found that the development of retail marketing is inextricably linked with the process of modernization of the domestic market, satisfying consumer needs and increasing the competitiveness of retail enterprises. The study developed methodological foundations for organizing effective activities in retail based on marketing strategies, market segmentation, sales promotion and brand management.

Also, practical recommendations were given to improve the effectiveness of retail marketing using analytical, comparative and empirical approaches. The results of the study show that the systematic and integrated use of the marketing complex, the development of digital technologies and interactive communication with customers ensure the sustainable growth and competitiveness of the retail system. As a result, the developed methodology serves as a scientific and practical foundation for the effective organization of marketing activities in retail enterprises, the development of the domestic market and the harmonization of local and foreign experience.

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